

D7.2 Risk Management and Contingency Monitoring Plan

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
GenA	General Assembly
LET'S CARE	Building safe and caring schools to foster educational inclusion and school
PC	Project Coordinator
PDER	Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results
PMAB	Policy Makers Advisory Board
TC	Technical Committee

1. Executive summary

LET'S CARE aims to understand and substantiate how student socio-emotional (in)security can promote/hinder educational opportunities from early childhood education to secondary school and beyond. The project, starting in October 2022, will analyse the forms and dynamics in which family relations and social inequality can explain school (under)achievement, (dis)engagement and early dropout, especially for vulnerable populations, and how building Safe School relationships can be a powerful tool to counteract these dynamics. This research will follow a methodological framework revolving around the theoretical and empirical exploration of the issue and the permeation of the project results through the policy action, fostering collaborative practices and elaborating the policy solutions. A co-creation and collaborative dynamics strategy throughout the project will be pursued.

The essential ethical and technical issues arising from the participation of many vulnerable minor participants and the possible effects that their involvement could have on their social inclusion and overall well-being (e.g., stigmatisation of students being identified as disadvantaged) require a robust Risk Assessment and Contingency Plan. This deliverable presents the risks that may arise during the project implementation and defines alternative implementation pathways.

2. Introduction

The Risk Assessment and Contingency Monitoring Plan is a tool to compile all risks identified during the project proposal development and alternative implementation pathways or mitigation actions. This plan also includes the strategy to identify unforeseen risks that may appear during the course of the project and guarantee that they are quickly addressed. D7.2 complements D7.9 "Data Management Plan", which covers a plan for the data collection, processing activities and storage during and after the project, that follows the requirements established in the Data Protection Legislation and the best practices for managing research data identified by the European Research Agency.

Different **foreseen risks** of implementation and management were identified in the project's proposal phase and confirmed upon the Grant Agreement signing and the Project Kick-off meeting. Therefore, all partners are aware of the existing risks identified for the project and are committed to implementing the mitigation measures to be taken. All risks identified will be monitored throughout the project.

During project implementation, the partners will pay particular attention to identifying and monitoring any **possible** internal and external unexpected **risks**, carrying out all the necessary mitigation actions as early as possible (see D7.1). Each Partner will be responsible for reporting

immediately to their respective WP Leader and the PC, any risky situation that may arise and affect the project objectives or their successful completion. Any change in the time schedule of deliverables or the allocated budget must be reported to the corresponding WP Leader or the PC. In case of problems or delays, the WP leader will be consulted, and he/she may set up task forces to take the necessary actions. If no resolution is reached, the GenA will be consulted and will establish mitigation plans to reduce the impact of the risk occurring.

Additionally, as a Continuous Reporting mechanism, WP leaders will update the information concerning the risks detected in each WPs, regarding both foreseen and unforeseen risks. The information provided should include a clear risk description, WPs affected, potential mitigation measures, if the risk happened or not, mitigation measures applied to the problem and any additional comment. This information must be updated in a shared document every two months (before every TC Meeting), and each WP leader should indicate, in their presentation, if the risks have taken place and if the mitigation measures were successfully applied. In case measurements could not be applied, the reason should also be indicated.

3. Risk Assessment and Contingency Monitoring Plan

A **five-step management plan** will be implemented to **detect, evaluate, and mitigate** the foreseen and unforeseen risks of the project (Figure 2):

STEP 1. Firstly, any emerging risk would be described. A first list of foreseen critical risks was elaborated on during the project's proposal. However, any possible risk identified between meetings of the technical committee will follow a similar description of what the risk involves, to which WP belongs, which are the contextualised causes and effects, and which mitigating actions have been proposed.

STEP 2. The second step involves a risk exposure evaluation based on a matrix that maps the level of impact and probability of occurrence of the identified risk (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Risk exposure matrix

STEP 3. The results of the risks assessment will allow the implementation of defined solutions or tailor alternative risk mitigation actions when needed.

STEP 4. Once agreed on the mitigation actions required, the responsible team will manage their implementation and monitoring.

STEP 5. After implementing mitigation actions, the team(s) in charge will reassess if the risk is still present or closed.

Figure 2. Risk evaluation management plan

4. Identified risks and mitigation actions

Below is a list of critical risks identified with the respective causes and effects, and alternative implementation pathways or mitigating actions are presented for each WP:

RISK No.		1
Work Packages involved		1
Risk description	Actors with less political and social power play a minor role.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be individual or social circumstances that make it difficult for the actors to participate actively in the project. The effect would be the lack of involvement of certain groups in the project.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	A detailed mapping will be elaborated at the project start, where roles and relations will be studied to ensure the inclusion of all relevant groups at equal conditions.	

RISK No.		2
Work Packages involved		1
Risk description	Trained teachers and members of networks leave their institutions.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be personal or working contingencies. The effect would be to have the necessity to replace the dropout person	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	Trainings will be directed at representatives of groups (GA section 1.2.1.2.4), who will act as connectors and will train other people in their groups. This way, knowledge will be socialised with as many people as possible.	

RISK No.		3
Work Packages involved		1
Risk description	Failure to involve stakeholders to commit to the project network.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the lack of organisation and anticipation of the task. The effect would be not having enough stakeholders to finish the project satisfactorily.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	T1.1 and T3.3 are based on participatory methodology involving a broad network of stakeholders. The network's creation relies on existing connections of all partners' networks. WP6 activities will also support the expansion phase.	

RISK No.		4
Work Packages involved		1, 4, 6
Risk description	LET'S CARE Hub does not reach its target audience and does not support co-creation.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the lack of knowledge necessary to use the HUB and communication within the project. The effect would be the lack of access by potential users of the HUB and the loss of its potential.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	Detailed tasks have been planned for maximising the impact of the LET'S CARE Hub. Fieldwork and school access will help disseminate the LET'S CARE Hub purposes.	

RISK No.		5
Work Packages involved		2, 3
Risk description	Panels of indicators are not fully representative due to the heterogeneity between countries and contexts.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the lack of standardisation of the dimensions due to a lack of experience. The effect would be a non-representative set of indicators and a decrease in the quality of the project.	

Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	The consortium has a wide range of experience and has defined a solid methodology to contemplate all existing sources of socio-educational indicators. Data collection and ICT solutions are designed to incorporate major modifications related to selected indicators when necessary.
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RISK No.		6
Work Packages involved		3, 5
Risk description	The excessive workload for teachers involved in data collection and piloting hampers needed involvement.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the lack of process efficiency management and time management. The effect would be inaccurate data collection and a floppy piloting execution.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	Trainings and workshops will be prepared professionally, involving people early in the planning stages, stressing their value in career progression and capacitation. Official recognition of the participation in project activities as in-service training for teachers will justify and motivate the participants.	

RISK No.		7
Work Packages involved		3, 5
Risk description	Difficulties in receiving official permission to carry out research.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the scarce management organisation. The effect would have fewer data than expected.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	Partners already use consolidated networks in their region and have a track record of similar research. Policymakers are included in the consortium or are committed to LET'S CARE through letters of support to grant access to education centres.	

RISK No.		8
Work Packages involved		4, 5
Risk description	Good practices identified remain at a theoretical level, and practical results are not observed in tools development and validation.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the lack of a cyclical return to the theory to monitor the implementation of the models. The effect would be discordance between theory and practice and hence a decrease in the quality of the model.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	LET'S CARE methodology has been designed to allow constant feedback loops between theoretical research, data collection and practical implementation. Tools will continuously evolve throughout the project, ensuring that new indicators, requirements, or data are included in the deployed solutions.	

RISK No.		9
Work Packages involved		4, 5
Risk description	IT and technological limitations.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the lack of communication with the IT partner of the project and/or the lack of resources to have proper technological tools. The effect would be a decrease in the possibility of the project and its quality.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	Additional allocation of resources will be studied if technological issues appear. LET'S CARE has IT experts (FHV) that will be in charge of the management of any.	

RISK No.		10
Work Packages involved		5, 6
Risk description	Change of educational ideology, policies, and government/local authorities' regulations.	
Causes and effects	The cause will be inherently in the local political system. The effect would be a gap between the project and the local reality.	

Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	LET'S CARE responds to the need to devise policy strategies to improve social inclusion and education at the European level. However, LET'S CARE tools will be developed to allow adaptability to local regulations. The daily work of each country's partners in education will guarantee instant knowledge of these changes.
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RISK No.		11
Work Packages involved		6
Risk description	Dissemination activities do not reach target groups or the visibility of the results.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be a lack of proper dissemination and communication plan. The effect would be the incapacity of the project to reach civil society.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	The consortium will devise a comprehensive PDER in WP6, identifying potential end users and defining clear strategies to reach each target group. All partners are active members of multiple committees, associations and clusters directly linked with relevant stakeholders. In case of low success in D&C activities, the plan will be reviewed according to the feedback received by the users.	

RISK No.		12
Work Packages involved		6
Risk description	Lack of interest and non-willingness of policymakers to participate in capacity building.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be ineffective communication of the importance of the project and a lack of policymakers' involvement plan. The effect would be the lack of policymakers' participation and hence the impossibility of influencing the policies.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	LET'S CARE PDER will define clear strategies to facilitate the full involvement of policymakers in project events, workshops, and dedicated meetings. Partners' expertise ensures that policy	

	papers will be practical and will appropriately address policymakers' needs, thanks to their involvement in the project and the PMAB.
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RISK No.		13
Work Packages involved		-
Risk description	Legal/ethical issues are not sufficiently addressed as they are not identified.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be a scarcity of perspectives on the ethical aspect of the research. The effect would be the impossibility of ethically running the data collection and program implementation.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	There is a dedicated WP to ensure a continuous debate on legal and ethical challenges. This was kicked off with an interactive workshop in M5. In addition, the specialised legal partner (TLX) will attend relevant meetings of other WP and support the LET'S CARE partners through the project to ensure ethical and legal compliance.	

RISK No.		14
Work Packages involved		-
Risk description	Legal or ethical issues, despite being identified, are not sufficiently addressed.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be an insufficiency of perspective on the ethical aspect of the research. The effect would be the impossibility of ethically running the data collection and program implementation.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	LET'S CARE legal expert, TLX, has the expertise and workforce to provide input and support flexibly where needed. If national expertise in countries is necessary, TLX has an extensive network of national experts. TLX will provide partners with relevant tools and support to ensure LET'S CARE legal and ethical compliance. Moreover, LET'S CARE will strictly follow the	

	legal requirements related to data processing and comply with EU regulations on data protection.
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RISK No.		15
Work Packages involved		1, 2, 3
Risk description	Issues related to translation and lack of communication because of language.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the assumption that everyone knows English and the non-prevention in case someone does not. The effect could be an inability to communicate with some project members and/or stakeholders.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	Professional translation services will be used in each country to ensure qualitative and quantitative data are translated into the respective language within each country to a professional standard.	

RISK No.		16
Work Packages involved		1, 2, 3
Risk description	Partners run out of budget due to changes and over-expenditure.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be the lack of a cost and expenditure planning. The effect would be not being able to complete some project tasks.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	The budget has been carefully prepared. Expenditures will be reviewed on a six-monthly basis, helping identify potential deviations. The Project Office will help the partners with internal redistributions or modifications if necessary.	

RISK No.		17
Work Packages involved		1, 2, 3
Risk description	A partner leaves the consortium or underperforms.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be due to personal or working circumstances. The effect would be a decrease in the quality of the project.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	There are a large number of partners in LET'S CARE which should be able to address any gap caused by a partner leaving. LET'S CARE partners belong to extensive networks they can access if additional fieldwork site is needed.	

RISK No.		18
Work Packages involved		1, 2, 3
Risk description	Lack of alignment with stated plan and objectives.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be a lack of coordination and communication within the project. The effect would be a decrease in the quality of the project.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	Regular WP and consortium meetings will ensure that activities are streamlined and lessons learnt are shared.	

RISK No.		19
Work Packages involved		1, 2, 3
Risk description	COVID-19 pandemic could lead to risks in day-to-day operations and management tasks.	
Causes and effects	The cause could be a worsening of the COVID-19 pandemic situation. The effect would be a change in the project schedule and/or a delay.	
Alternative implementation pathways or Mitigating Actions	All partners have tools for virtual communication that will be broadly used to guarantee continuous communication in case travels are restricted. Protective measures and safety protocols for data collection and piloting school activities will be defined according to each country's regulations.	

5. Conclusions

This deliverable intends to show the strategy that will be used to monitor and limit risks that may arise during the project implementation. The risk matrix will be helpful during all the phases described above to evaluate the risk exposure of each work package and the possibility that foreseen and unforeseen risks may create serious issues.